

MAIN PROBLEMS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF A READING CULTURE IN YOUTH

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical aspect of reading culture and its development among young people as the main factor in the formation of his personal qualities, analyzes the content and the structure of this activity and offers separate directions for its possible implementation in practice.

Keywords: Reading, reading culture, reception, youth, public policy, local governments, institutions.

Reading has played an important and integral role since ancient times in the upbringing of the personality, the disclosure of its individual characteristics, and also served as an important factor in its formation.

In this regard, in the modern world, reading should take a special place, first of all, in the system of continuous education, including in the daily activities of everyone, and reading culture is the basis of the social, cognitive, artistic, aesthetic and spiritual development of a modern personality, especially youth.

In Uzbekistan, close attention is paid to reading and reading culture, and this issue is relevant and brought to the level of state policy.

President of Uzbekistan back in March 2019 put forward five initiatives aimed at creating additional conditions for the upbringing and education of young people and increasing the employment of women. The fourth initiative envisages increasing the spirituality of young people, widespread promotion of reading. The head of state noted the need to awaken young people from childhood to love books, to form independent thinking and a broad outlook, which, in his opinion, will become a solid foundation in their way of life.

Taking into account the current situation, he proposed a number of specific solutions, that is, to create conditions for the development of this direction or the so-called. "Techniques" for the development of a culture of reading among young people. Among these measures:

the publication of books on art, educational and social topics within the framework of the "Caravan of Education" project and delivery of at least 1 million copies to all regions;

creation of one sample bookstore in each city and district center;

provision of library services to the population of villages and auls through

the placement of mobile book pavilions in all cities and regions;
creation of "Bibliobus".

These measures are a consistent continuation of the Strategy of Action in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, in which, within the framework of the priority areas of development of the social sphere, special attention is paid to the following issues:

education of physically healthy, spiritually and intellectually developed, independently thinking, devoted to the Motherland of youth with firm views of life...;

support and realization of the creative and intellectual potential of the young generation...

Thus, one of the important factors in achieving these goals is reading and, in general, the development of a reading culture, in connection with which one should turn to their concept and essence.

Reading is one of the types of speech activity, which consists in the perception of written visually and reproduction aloud or to oneself. Reading in the newest encyclopedic dictionary is cited as a specific form of linguistic communication between people through printed or handwritten texts, one of the main forms of mediated communication.

Reading is also defined as a basic component of upbringing, education and cultural development. It is an activity that forms and develops a personality, an instrument for obtaining education and disseminating culture, evidence of the formation of a specialist's communicative and professional competence, an instrument for achieving a person's success in life.

Reading is not a one-sided effect of works on the reader, expressed in passive perception, assimilation of the content of the text, and active interaction between communicators (text creators) and recipients (readers). Reading is a creative process and individualizing, which greatly enhances its versatile impact on the personality. It must be considered as a set of differentiated ways of introducing culture, differing depending on the type and type of publication, the nature and purpose of the text.

Modern society is at the stage of post-industrial development, which is characterized by a new information space, characterized, among other things, by the powerful development of audiovisual means of transmitting information. The latter have a significant impact on the reading process: on the one hand, they lead away from reading, and on the other hand, they allow one to obtain information in other ways.

To become a reader you need to learn. We need a culture of reading, that is, reading in the broad sense of the word as one of the most important practices in modern societies. In the scientific literature there is no clear definition of the concept of "reading culture". Summarizing theoretical studies, the experts offer a working definition of the concept of "reading culture". Reading culture is understood as a certain level of formation of a number of reading skills and abilities:

- need in reading and a strong interest in it; reading erudition;
- reading skills, expressive reading skills;
- the ability to perceive various literary works, elementary bibliographic knowledge;
- the required level of theoretical and literary knowledge;
- creative abilities;
- assessment and interpretation skills;
- speech skills.

The level of reader interest among young people is significantly reduced. Reading literature is viewed by them as a compulsory, unattractive phenomenon. The urgent task today is to revive the interest in conscious reading. The system of forming reading skills, of course, must be flexible and adapt to the artistic method of the writer.

Thus, the issues of the culture of reading in general and the methods of its development among young people in particular can be considered in various dimensions and meanings. For example, in the system of continuing education – starting from preschool to postgraduate, as well as in the daily activities of the individual, taking into account the presence in society of such categories of young people in terms of employment – organized and unorganized.

In the Oxford Dictionary, the word "technique" is defined as a way of doing something. Based on this, in terms of organization and implementation, the methods of developing a culture of reading among young people can be conditionally divided into two directions, that is, with organized youth and unorganized among them. At the same time, an analysis of the available research shows that this issue has been comprehensively studied to a certain extent and many techniques, methods and forms of the development of reading culture in preschool institutions, among students and working youth have been proposed. The question of attracting an unorganized part of young people to reading remains topical.

Aware of the fact that the way in which the issue of involving young people

in reading is implemented or practiced is strongly intertwined with measures to create conditions for this, they should also be considered in the same plane with the methods of development.

So, an example of such a technique is the discovery in the National Park of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi in Tashkent Alley of writers. The head of state recommended the transformation of the Alley of Writers into a center of culture, spirituality and education, especially for young people, holding poetry evenings, book presentations, exhibitions and educational events here.

And this, in turn, will contribute to strengthening the faith of young people in tomorrow, generating a talented and creative among them, acquainting students with the work of prominent artists and their peers, fostering love for poetry, reading, uniting the community of students, parents with the idea of popularizing the literary creativity of gifted children and adolescents, the development of the ability to listen, empathize and sympathize, the formation of interest in creative literary activity. It is this that can serve as a vivid example as one of the techniques and positive experiences that should be developed in other regions of the country.

As other methods, along with the ways proposed by the President, one can propose the implementation of projects on:

- making this problem locally one of the important tasks of local government and self-government;

- creation of mini-libraries in each mahalla, taking into account the interests of the local population;

 - intensifying local advisory work with aspiring readers;

 - conducting various competitions among unorganized youth;

- determination of the best family and mahalla in this area and their every possible encouragement;

- publishing of fiction books, comprehensive support of entrepreneurs in this area;

- conducting on-site meetings, various round tables and other interesting events of a character that attracts reading.

It also seems expedient to create audiobooks, various television and radio programs dedicated to the fiction book, discuss literary novelties on the air of regional televisions with the involvement of young people from among unorganized youth. It is important that in order to achieve these goals, this activity should not be carried out on a one-time basis, but turned into a systematic and permanent work.

Thus, the formation in modern conditions of the value orientations of the population, first of all, youth as the most dynamic part of society, is one of the main problems, goals and directions of youth policy.

Therefore, in any society and state, the value orientations of the individual, youth are the object of education, and the process of their education is an important direction of youth policy for the implementation of spiritual, moral, patriotic and labor education.

In this regard, an important aspect is the development of a reading culture among young people by creating all the necessary conditions for this.

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